

JOB STRESS AMONG WOMEN EMPLOYEES

G. Gnanaselvi* & Dr. S. Shanmugapriya**

* Assistant Professor & Ph.D (PT) Research Scholar, PG & Research Department of Commerce, NGM College, Pollachi, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

** Assistant Professor & Research Guide, PG & Research Department of Commerce, NGM College, Pollachi, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: G. Gnanaselvi & Dr. S. Shanmugapriya, "Job Stress among Women Employees", International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 170-174, 2018.

Copy Right: © IJCRME, 2018 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

Stress is defined as "a state of psychological and physiological imbalance resulting from the disparity between situational demand and the individual's ability and motivation to meet those needs." Stress has often been misunderstood to be negative, with few people acknowledging the importance and usefulness of positive stress. In our everyday lives, stress is everywhere and definitely unavoidable; hence our emphasis should be on differentiating between what is good stress, and what is bad. Stress is one of the most important things that play a major role in human life. The main objective is to find out the level of stress among the women employees of different age groups and to identify the effective dimension of stress among women employees. For this a sample of 70 was collected from the women employees of IT industry were t-test, Anova, percentage analysis and mean scores are used as tools to analyze the data and the conclusion is that level of acceptance towards withdrawal has an influence towards the age of the respondents and age has to be taken in to consideration for the decision making process when taking decision on the factors related to level of acceptance towards withdrawal with the respondents and while taking decision on level of acceptance towards work performance the factors related to perception towards psychological symptoms has to be taken for decision making process of the study. There is a positive impact towards behavioral symptoms and negative impact towards physical symptoms with women employees. The IT industry can empower staff to control their own workload and consider whether it is appropriate to provide additional support for staff during periods of change and uncertainty.

Key Words: Stress, Psychological Symptoms & Workload

Introduction:

In our day to day life, stress is everywhere and definitely unavoidable. One finds stress everywhere, whether be it within the family, business organization or any other social or economic activity. Right from the time of birth till the last breath, every individual is invariably exposed to various stressful situations. Stress happens whenever one's mind and body react to some real or imagined situation. Since every condition or event in our body life causes some degree or stress, it is unrealistic and impossible to totally eliminate stress from one's life. Urbanization, industrialization and increase in the scale of operation in the society are causing increasing stresses. Stress can have serious consequences for both health and work performance. In terms of health, the current belief among many medical practitioners is that 50 to 70% of all physical illnesses are related to stress. Stress can cause depression, irritation, anxiety, fatigue, lowered self-esteem and reduced job satisfaction. Sustained over a long period, stress can lead to attempts to escape through the use of drug or alcohol.

Statement of the Problem:

Stress is one of the most important things that play a major role in human life. Since all the companies depend upon man power, it is one of the important issues to be taken care of and also it has become a major concern of the modern times. Stress can cause harm to women employee's health and performance. Work related stress may lead to sickness, high turnover and high absenteeism. Job stress is a condition arising from the interaction of people that force deviate from their timing. So it becomes necessary for every organization to know about the level of stress among the employees and its consequences so that the IT industry can overcome it.

Objective of the Study:

- ✓ To find out the level of stress among the employees of different age groups.
- ✓ To identify the factors causing stress among the women employees.
- ✓ To analyze the level of acceptance towards work performance.
- ✓ To offer suitable suggestion on the basis of findings of the study.

Need for the Study:

The need of the study is that as the women employees have stress towards their work based on different reasons it has to be minimized to reduce the stress in future period of time.

Scope of the Study:

- ✓ Stress will badly affect the women employees both at work place and in personal life. If stress is managed properly.
- ✓ It is beneficial to women employees as well as the organization in terms of production, improved relationships both on and off the job. Also it leads to better teamwork and communication.
- ✓ The employee's turnover will be low and the absenteeism rate will be lower. Also the retention of valued employees is possible.

Conceptual Frame Work:

Research Methodology:

Research Design: The study was conducted in order to find out the employee stress towards IT industry.

Sampling Design & Tools Applied:

Sampling Techniques: Sampling unit can be defined as the basic unit containing the stress towards IT industry.

Sampling Size: In this research, the sample size amount to seventy, which are surveyed from women employees of IT industry.

Sampling Type: Convenience sampling is adapted in this research. It is a non-probability sampling and it refers to selecting a sample based on convenience.

Data Collection: The primary data the respondents which or collected with a questionnaire schedule was used with women employees with the industry.

Secondary data were collected from manuals, journals, magazines and newspapers etc.

Research Tool: Structures self administered questionnaire had been used as a research tool for collecting.

Method of Data Collection: The questionnaire from is designed in the multi choice pattern and has the following technique.

Direct Questions: In this type, the respondents were asked to answer directly to their questions.

Indirect Questions: Indirect questions refer to those whose responses are used to indicate or suggest information.

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ The sample size is limited to 70.
- ✓ There is a bias with the collection of data as the respondents may wrong answers for the questions asked to the

Analysis and Interpretation:

Demographic Variables of the Respondents

Particulars		Frequency	Percent
Age	18-25	41	58.6
	26-30	29	41.4
	Total	70	100.0
Marital Status	Single	68	97.1
	Married	02	2.9
	Total	70	100.0
Experience	1-5	26	37.1

Particulars		Frequency	Percent
Age	18-25	41	58.6
	26-30	29	41.4
	5-10	19	27.1
	11-15	20	28.6
	16 and above	05	7.1
	Total	70	100.0
Income level	Below 10000	13	18.6
	10000-20000	38	54.3
	Above 20000	19	27.1
	Total	70	100.0

Interpretation:

Major number of respondents belongs to the category between 18-25 where they would have initial experience towards their job description. According to C. Balakrishnamurthy and Swetha Shankar (2009), age has a strong relationship towards stress level of women employees. Majority of the respondents are single in our survey as majority of the respondents are from the age group between 18-25 they are yet to get married. Based on the research majority of the respondents are having experience between 1-5 years.

Work Performance of the Employees:

It discusses about the mean scores related to work performance of the employees were the average mean value for the factors related to level of acceptance towards work performance of the employees is at 3.

S.No	Particulars	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean Score
Work Performance							
1	Declining/inconsistent performance	8	15	38	9	0	2.69
2	Uncharacteristic	7	26	16	16	5	2.80
3	Loss of control over work	13	27	20	5	5	2.46
4	Loss of motivation/communication	11	8	13	16	22	3.43
5	Increased time at work	32	15	10	13	0	3.06

Interpretation:

The mean value of acceptance towards loss of motivation and communication (3.43) and acceptance towards increased time at work (3.06) are higher than 3. It shows that the employees are not accepting for the factors and remedy measures has to be taken for the factors related to the above said factors. As an employer, it is important to look at things from the employee's perspective and realize that they are most likely not in the same place you are, whether professionally, financially, or even personally. It is important to be able to empathize with the employees. Get up and moving—don't sit in a desk job for more than an hour at a time

Comparison between Level of Acceptance towards Work Performance and Various Symptoms of Stress:

H01: There is no significant relationship between level of acceptance towards work performance and Perception towards Psychological symptoms

Paired Samples Test						
Particulars		Paired Differences		t	DF	Sig. (2-tailed)
		95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
		Upper				
H01	Level of acceptance towards work performance - Perception towards Psychological symptoms	-.04837		-2.793	149	.006
H02	Level of acceptance towards Aggressive behavior - Perception towards Behavioral symptoms	-.09559		-3.036	148	.003
H03	Level of acceptance towards Regression - Perception towards Physical symptoms	.00210		-1.937	149	.055

Interpretation:

The above table with part 1 shows about the relationship between level of acceptance towards work performance and perception towards Psychological symptoms were the level of significance is at 0.006 which is

lesser than 0.05. It shows that there is a relationship between level of acceptance towards work performance and perception towards Psychological symptoms.

Relationship Between Age and Factors Related to Stress:

H01: There is no significant relationship between age and Level of acceptance towards work performance

H02: There is no significant relationship between age and Level of acceptance towards withdrawal

H03: There is no significant relationship between age and Level of acceptance towards Regression

Particulars		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F	Sig
Level of acceptance towards work performance	18-25	41	2.9366	.71476	.382	.539
	26-30	29	2.8138	.94858		
	Total	70	2.8857	.81548		
Level of acceptance towards withdrawal	18-25	41	2.9268	.72492	4.326	.041
	26-30	29	2.5793	.63323		
	Total	70	2.7829	.70505		
Level of acceptance towards Regression	18-25	41	2.9085	.62937	.779	.380
	26-30	29	2.7845	.49877		
	Total	70	2.8571	.57825		
Level of acceptance towards Aggressive behavior	18-25	41	2.9366	.70914	1.088	.301
	26-30	29	3.0897	.41261		
	Total	70	3.0000	.60529		
Perception towards Psychological symptoms	18-25	41	3.1073	.60349	1.298	.259
	26-30	29	2.9379	.62588		
	Total	70	3.0371	.61413		
Perception towards Behavioral symptoms	18-25	41	3.3073	.93925	199	.657
	26-30	29	3.2207	.54075		
	Total	70	3.2714	.79494		
Perception towards Physical symptoms	18-25	41	2.9366	.71195	.012	.912
	26-30	29	2.9172	.73196		
	Total	70	2.9286	.71508		

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the relationship between age and factors related to stress where there is a relationship between age and level of acceptance towards withdrawal as the level of significance is less than 0.05.

Findings and Suggestions:

- ✓ Major number of respondents belongs to the category between 18-25 where they would have initial experience towards their job description.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents are single in our survey as majority of the respondents are from the age group between 18-25 they are yet to get married.

- ✓ The employees are not accepting for the factors and remedy measures has to be taken for the factors related to the above said factors.
- ✓ The employees are not accepting for the factors and remedy measures has to be taken for the factors related to the above said factors.
- ✓ The factors show their emotions to their family, hard for them to relax at home and finding it hard to talk when they get excited. Related to level of acceptance towards psychological symptoms is lesser than 3 and it shows that the employees have negative perception towards the above said factors.

Conclusion:

The conclusion is that level of acceptance towards withdrawal has an influence towards the age of the respondents and age has to be taken in to consideration for the decision making process when taking decision on the factors related to level of acceptance towards withdrawal with the respondents and while taking decision on level of acceptance towards work performance the factors related to perception towards Psychological symptoms has to be taken for decision making process of the study.

References:

1. K. Aswathappa, 2008, Human Resource Management, 5th ed., Tata McGraw-Hill Companies, New Delhi.
2. Saiyadain, Mirza, 2008, Organisational Behaviour, 1st ed., Tata McGraw-Hill Companies, New Delhi.
3. Baty, B. (2002). Managing Stress at Work. Clearwater 2010 Stress Best Practice Paper, Retrieved from. <http://www.workstress.net/downloads/clearwater%202010%20project.doc>. Beena, C. & Poduval, P. R. (1992). Gender difference in Work of Executives. Psychological Studies Journal, 37(2&3), 109-113.
4. Bhatia, A. L., Sushila, P & Kaur, S. (2008). Gender differences in Coping Styles and Life Satisfaction of Teachers in Higher Education. Journal of Psychological Researches, 52(2), 99-104.
5. Bhatnagar, D. & Bose, K. (1985). Organizational Role Stress and Branch Managers. Prajnan, 14(4), 349-360. 78 OPUS Volume 4 Annual Journal 2013 Bianchi, E. (2004). Stress and Coping among Cardiovascular Nurses: A Survey in Brazil. Issues in Mental Health Nursing, 25(7), 737-745.
6. Kelly, T. & Barrett, M. (2012). The Leading Causes and Potential Consequences of Occupational Stress: A Study of Irish Trainee Accountants. IAR2012.indb.
7. Laal, M. & Aliramaie, N. (2010). Nursing and Coping with Stress. International journal of collaborative Research on Internal Medicine & Public Health, 2(5), 168-181.
8. Lai, G., Chan, K. B., Ko, Y. C., & Boey, K. W. (2000). Institutional Context and Stress Appraisal: The Experience of Life Insurance Agents in Singapore. Journal of Asian & African Studies, 35, 209-228